

THE ROLE OF HISTORY IN FORMING A PERFECT MAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13081975>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 17th July 2024

Accepted: 18th July 2024

Published: 27th July 2024

KEYWORDS

philosophical anthropology , perfect man , good the word is good verb , good ethics and Education , Sufism , Qasidai advice "

ABSTRACT

Man essence philosophical in terms of deeper analysis to do for Muhammadreza Ogahi's anthropological their views study , his in his works illuminated to a person special social attributes , qualities and education education , work , knowledge , various relationship , moral of norms formation and socialization philosophical in terms of open to give today's of the day current from the topics one is considered Our people spiritual of the world formation and development strong effect showed , science is science development and perfect to be for service did of our people spiritual , mystical-philosophical thinking in enrichment separately place held Muhammadreza Ogahi's works today's to the day until humanity spiritual in the inheritance big important have that display this of the article main purpose is considered Also in it Muhammadreza Ogahi's anthropological in his views of a person spiritual to the world come in to go through a person essence deeper understanding and perfect a person formation that it is possible idea too to see can

Nowadays, it is one of the most important subjects that to organize the anthropological views of Mukhammadrizo Ogachi for a deeper philosophical analysis of human nature, philosophical disclosure of human social qualities, qualities and education, labor, knowledge, various relationships, the formation and socialization of moral norms reflected in his works. To show that the works of Mukhammadrizo Ogachi , who had a strong impact on the formation and development of the spiritual world of our people, played a special role in enriching the spiritual, mystical and philosophical thinking of our people, have played a significant role in the spiritual heritage of mankind is the main goal of this article. The works of Muhammadrizo Ogahi , who had a strong influence on the formation and development of the spiritual world of

our people, served for the development and perfection of science, and played a special role in enriching the spiritual, mystical and philosophical thinking of our people, are of great importance in the spiritual heritage of mankind to this day. Keywords: philosophical anthropology, perfect man, good word, good action, good morals and education, Sufism, "Qasidai advice".

History individuals, societies and of cultures to himself feature and external appearance in formation solution doer role plays. We ourselves and others perception that's all we can do including external to our appearance historical come our exit big effect shows. This in the essay i of history personal in changes to the role attention directed without, a person appearance in formation of history importance discussion i do. In particular, historical event and narratives of the person himself himself understanding and external apparently how effect to show possible seeing I'll go out, that's it artistic hero Perfect in the example example I bring Perfect of change to himself special aspects from learning before, of history a person to the image how effect to do wider to understand need. History during different different social norms, cultural practices and political events of people physical features and himself himself imagination in doing important role played. For example, beauty concept time pass with colonialism, globalization and technological development such as factors under the influence of formed. This historical effects beauty standards to create take came, they most of the time real didn't happen and a lot people for achieved it won't be.

From colonialism next in society living a guy Perfect in the example his himself in the sense of external in the form of history deep place holds. Centuries during colonialism and oppression under formed in society grown up Perfect own to the people app done beauty and success about dominant stories own into takes. As a result, it is this to standards compliance to do for pressure conducts and success and of beauty idealized to the image suitable coming external appearance to change strives. Perfect himself change trip of history personal to himself characteristic and external to look more social effect reflection makes. Perfect his own physical features cosmetic procedures and another tools through to change striving, strength, privilege and beauty about historical in narratives deep root shot himself himself again invention to do process with is engaged. His external appearance to change his desire to himself feature and identity understanding feeling formed of history cruel to the forces resistance show shape as to see can.

From this except, of Kamil change personal authority and historical determinism between complicated mutually dependence emphasizes. Perfect his own external appearance change to the right have although - his selection in the end beauty and success about concept formed historical forces by limited. In this sense Perfect himself to change has been aspiration historical oppression and marginalization conditions representation and powers for wider social of struggles the opposite being service does of history Perfect himself perception reach and external apparently effect complete understanding for collective memory and cultural to the individual self of memory characteristic in formation role account get necessary. Perfect like from colonialism next in society historical stories most of the time to debates reason will be and again seeing will be released, this people himself and others how acceptance to do effect to do possible has been of the past one how many to versions take will come. Perfect own appearance to change decision in making own to the people embedded negative from molds, historical from injustices get away desire reason to be can.

Besides, Kamil's change, as well as marginalized teams experience aside to push and no to do striving of history dominant to stories against personal resistance show shape see also as can. Perfect his own external appearance changing to himself characteristic emphasizing to himself special to the feature have being his self feeling designation and to manage striving historical to the forces against is struggling. Thus Kamil's himself change the way historical injustice and oppression opposite submission and to power have of being strong to

the story becomes History people , societies and cultures perception reach and to understand our style in formation solution doer role plays This to us of people in the past did behavior and decisions to understand for necessary the context present is enough and As a result our point of view our view and to them has been to our relationship effect does Perfect a person in the example his own formation and in the change of history importance reducing it won't be .

Various strong and weak to the parties have person expressive fantastic hero Perfect a person his historical condition is a product . His faith , values and behavior himself living period events , traditions and ideologies effect shows . His society history study through Perfect a person formed , his person being to reach reason has been factors deeper our understanding can of history Perfect a person of the person formation effect reach methods one his culture traditions and traditions . These are traditions from generation to generation past , his belief and values message will give . For example , Kamil a person the family everyone from the thing superior who eats from culture came out if so , it is his relatives and ancestors with relationships the first to the seat to put , own personality family and to society directed person as formation can Besides , history Perfect to a person concern , his to the roots contact feeling will give . He is himself to society effect showed historical events realize reach through own legacy with strong connected with his ancestors struggles and victories with get to know can This is history feeling Perfect of a person who and Where that he came deeper understanding through his identity to form help will give .

Besides , history Perfect a person for inspiration source become him difficulties overcame to move on , to encourage him towards his dreams can In difficulties to greatness achieved historical of individuals stories learning their from their experiences strength and encouragement take can This is historic conditions Perfect in man to the thickets endurance and persistence feelings absorb through his identity formation can Besides , history Perfect of a person perception reach and others with to the relationship effect to do can Various different people groups between historical mutually relationships learning , it is different come output has been to individuals relatively more to understand and empathy development can This historical context Perfect of a person to himself characteristic formation possible they are differently from being strict look at others relatively inclusiveness and acceptance to do feeling wakes up .

Besides , history Perfect of a person power dynamics and social hierarchy about concept also a role in formation game can In society power distribution effect showed historical events learning through that authority structures activity and people to his life effect to do methods understand can This historical context Perfect to a person in society inequalities and injustices orientation and to them against in fighting help to give through his identity formation can Besides , history Perfect of a person manners to the feeling effect to do can In the past people face came moral hesitations and their of behavior consequences learning through it goodness and wrongness more feel stronger takes This is historic context Perfect of a person decision acceptance to do and behavior leadership to do through his identity to form , ultimately to become striving person type effect to do can

Summary by doing to say If so , Kamil a person identity formation and in the change history important role plays To him heritage , inspiration , sympathy and ethics feeling to give through history his himself , others and around the world how perception to reach effect does Perfect a person his own historical conditions deeper understanding through himself awareness , perseverance and kindness feelings more strengthen will get , in the end him knowledgeable , sympathetic and moral conscious person as forms . Perfect such as of individuals external appearance and own in understanding history important role plays Historical events and of narratives personal to changes effect to do methods learning through we private agency and historical determinism between complicated mutually the effect

deeper our understanding can Perfect story of history personal self and external to look constant influence , historical oppression opposite representation and power for continue doing fight sharp note being service does Our past legacy with in fighting continue enough beauty , success and own our dignity in formation of history recognize the role and everyone for more inclusive and fair society Create to act on the way necessary

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INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY